

Teachers by before school education organization in pupils passable training in the process to the children applied pedagogical communication styles classification

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Abstract: The article analyzes the classification of pedagogical communication styles used by pedagogues during training. In addition, by using the method of pedagogical communication correctly, the manners of preschoolers, aspects related to information acquisition are reflected in the article. The impact of pedagogical communication methods on the mastering process in the teacher's professional activity has been thoroughly analyzed.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется влияние методов педагогического общения на процесс усвоения в профессиональной деятельности учителя. Кроме того, в статье отражены правильное использование метода педагогического общения, манеры поведения дошкольников, аспекты, связанные с усвоением информации. Подробно проанализировано влияние методов педагогического общения на процесс усвоения в профессиональной деятельности учителя.

mastering process in the teacher's professional activity has been thoroughly analyzed.

Key words: Communication, pedagogical communication, educational system, communication methods, way of thinking, speech culture, learning process and etiquette, professional activity.

Ключевые слова: Общение, педагогическое общение, образовательная система, методы общения, образ мышления, культура речи, учебный процесс и этикет, профессиональная деятельность.

When a person comes into the world, he begins to study the environment and analyze it. The universe first his parents through after he begins to perceive before school education in the institution education givers , later at school pedagogues by realize developed goes _ He begins to study all the creatures in the world around him through his senses. As he develops mentally and quantitatively, he needs to express his opinion. His interest in getting more pleasure from the things he likes increases. It tries to explain the aspects that it does not like. And this him wrapping standing universe and in it people with to communicate introduction just like that is enough Through this n win development and communication process forming goes _ Speech development at the time it is many the words first no _ not understanding until school _ education at the age of When he arrived, he said the words the meaning mentally understand use starts _ In this process parents asset activity shows socialization _ as a result before school education in the institution education givers by strengthened , the surrounding with conscious to communicate enters , own his opinion means and others the word understand goes _

Dialogue is a Greek word that means conversation, interpersonal conversation, and exchange of ideas, and occurs in the speech of two or more people . Two and more than that, it is a process of exchange of ideas between people.¹

Pedagogical communication means the system, methods and skills of mutual action between the pedagogue and the group of students consisting of information exchange, educational impact and mutual cooperation. The teacher is the initiator of this process, organizes

¹PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS; Tashkent; "ECONOMY-FINANCE"-2011 page 117

it and leads it. ANLeontev, evaluating the educational and didactic importance of pedagogical communication, expresses the following points. Active pedagogical communication is the key of the teacher, the pedagogical team in general, to know and learn the students in the educational process, and the creative character of the educational activity, which creates the best conditions for the formation of the student's personality. providing an acceptable emotional environment in education, including preventing the emergence of mental and psychological barriers, ensuring proper management of social and psychological processes in the children's community, and in the educational process is an important tool that creates opportunities for the teacher to use his pedagogical skills wisely.² The didactic and especially educational tasks of the teacher's activity cannot be carried out in a sufficiently productive manner without organizing a productive process of communication between the teacher and the group of students.

V.A. Kan-Kalik emphasizes that pedagogical communication is made up of relationships and methods of interaction and categorizes them as follows:

1) communication based on interest in collaborative creative work. In a dialogue based on interest in creative work carried out in cooperation, the pedagogue has a positive attitude towards learners and work.

2) communication based on friendly relations. Communication based on friendly relations is close to the type of communication discussed above. Some pedagogues misunderstand friendly communication and cross the line. There should be a certain distance between the teacher and the student. The teacher's culture and pedagogical tact play an important role in determining this distance.

3) communication that keeps the teacher and students at a certain distance. Communication that keeps a certain distance cannot be considered effective either. However, this is a common method. There is a certain boundary between the pedagogue and the students, which can be described as follows: "I know - you don't know", "Do as I say - I am older, more experienced, we cannot be equal". This method is closer to the authoritarian one, which from the outside seems to help to implement orderly activities, but does not give high efficiency.

4) communication based on intimidation. A high-level form of communication that keeps teachers and learners at a distance is bullying communication. It embodies a negative attitude towards learners and authoritarian rule. As a vivid expression of this style, the following statements can be cited: "Listen carefully, otherwise I will leave you two", "I will still show you your days". This style creates a negative atmosphere during training.

that a person is not born into the world with a fully formed character, moral characteristics program, his characteristic qualities, moral standards are the product of social life and family upbringing. During this formation, the role of the information given in the preschool educational institution and the activities conducted is significant.

First of all, it is necessary to teach children to overcome fear, hesitation and lack of courage. Because you can't teach a child to swim without putting him in the water. In fact, it is difficult to overcome the fear and lack of courage in children or young school students without testing them in situations that require courage and bravery.

² Khalikov A. Pedagogical skill Tashkent "ECONOMY-FINANCE" 2011
www.ziyouz.com library page 78

Kaikovus (11th century) in his "Nightmare" talked about teaching children a trade, and in his advice to his children, he also talked about the culture of treatment of children by parents and teachers. For example, he says that a parent can influence a child through a teacher in order to inculcate knowledge and moral qualities in his ³child : (Father) show compassion, be kind , my young son learns manners with a stick and does not learn by his own will. But if the child is impudent and you get angry because of that , don't beat him with your own hand, scare him with the teacher's stick. Let the teachers teach the children so that your son does not hold a grudge against you .⁴

If we want to raise our young people to be brave, brave and fearless, we need a different approach to this work. Because the romantic stage of the history of education, the education of courage, is behind us. Developed countries have already moved to its technological stage.

Raising children to be intelligent and wise, active and resourceful, brave and courageous depends first of all on the parents and then on the educators who are responsible for the upbringing of the child. We should try to arm them with the most modern advanced knowledge.

Therefore, educators should educate students to be the most reliable young people on earth . We can become one of the leading nations only if we are willing to do this . Otherwise, they will have to live by buying rather than discovering and buying products.

The more pedagogues are on this path, the more different methods and tools are used, the faster the goal is achieved. Pedagogy does not create its methods out of nothing, it does not invent them. He selects from life the real factors of people's behavior, those who meet the tasks of organizing students' lives in a pedagogically appropriate way, and uses the quality of methods of pedagogical influence in educational work. Pedagogical impact methodology consists of a system of tools used to organize children's social and useful activities in a pedagogically appropriate manner. These tools are aimed at the individual of the student, stimulate the behavior of those who enter the dialogue, their difficult and complex tasks become a source of creative pleasure, their personal interests.

The communication style chosen by the pedagogue plays an especially important role in the initial period of working with the group of communicators, in the first lessons. At this stage, how things go in the group, how accurately this or that action is performed by the students, and how the relationship between the teacher and the student begins, the students consider him a respected friend - their leader. Whether they will admit it or not, all this is closely related to the requirements of the educator.

Thus, in the initial period of working with communication starters and organizing new types of their activities, the requirements of the pedagogue are an important means of encouraging the necessary behavior of students, as well as a means of preventing and stopping undesirable and useless actions. will be We will look at the main groups and forms of demand.

Educator's demands can be direct demands, in which they are aimed at such students that the educator expects them to achieve certain actions, or the educator's demands can be instrumental demands, in which the teacher with his demands makes the students next in line with their peers. makes demands.

³Malla Ochilov "Teacher is the architect of the heart" Tashkent "Teacher" 2001 p. 27

⁴Nightmare. Tashkent, "Heritage", 1992, p. 83

First of all, we will describe the main forms of demand, the choice of one or another form of this method is related to taking into account the pedagogical situation. Pedagogical situation for direct requirements arises from two main conditions, two factors. First factor - from whom Demand kilinsa, that's it Demand to the doer has been is a relationship. Second factor is _ of the pupil pedagogue encouraging to activity i is a relationship. In general when this relations we are positive, neutral and negative we define as relations, whereas in practice this of relationships very more and more to have appearances as well can _

Now Demand to the forms stopping let's go Demand straight up to be can, in this of the teacher address « So and only so do » according to the formula b' in a strong, bold mood _ expressed sure to the instruction have will be Such without students _ to action exclamation point factor of demand himself is considered

The ball is right Demand the team with of work the first stage especially impressive will be This one writer showing past was: " Sincere, open, convincing, passionate strictly Demand if not, the team to educate starting from it won't happen, therefore, anyone has it of the ambiguities, given and _ _ shuvab from those who leave the work to start if he thinks, he is wrong did will be ".

Teacher students for new has been activity organize doing the ball is right in the place Demand is necessary. Here _ straight up Demand of education initial method has been the road is the path to give like go to himself attention attraction does _ Saying that _ let 's go straight Demand most of the time of the student to the pedagogue or he started to the activity neutral in relation to be conditions is used. Such in the situation ball- directly, directly of demand the following to the rules compliance to do especially important _

First rule: usually, requirement positive to be, that is absolutely certain behavior cause output, students' it or this actions just not to prohibit, not to stop Of course, the teacher from prohibitions especially, students defined behavior the rules each different way has been h ols is used. However pedagogues requirements main content prohibitions organize ca n't In the requirements main thing students behavior and of activity positive is a program.

Second rule: the ball is correct Demand guidance in the style, that is one different meaningful, clear and clear, concrete to be it is necessary Initial times of students new actions when encouraged Demand the road is the path to give with by joining as if gone it will be actions detailing them _ sure by describing will give.

Third rule: pedagogue's somehow reasonable, clear and prepared straight up demand of course completion, to the end delivered need. That remember catch should be similar pedagogical movement of the law manifestation to be as a result each one new of demand execution of the pedagogue next requirements of power and effectiveness increases student - teacher intelligence with sure submission habit forms. And on the contrary, har one not done Demand from that next of requirements efficiency lower a di. The ball is correct of requirements technical performance about when speaking, them to put firm, reliable tone emphasizing tooth _ need _ He is calm about the situation look, seriously to be, but never time to shout, child an insult to do turning around not stay need _ Demand-consultation trainee to his mind distrust from reporting consists of is, it is or this behavior, practical task different method of solving to the goal compatibility about includes the teacher's recommendation to make a decision independently. Like a request, the advice is not forced, the right to choose remains with the child. This form develops a conscious attitude to work and, in addition, teaches to

consider the pedagogue as an older comrade, whose reputation is based on the fact that it is hidden in wide knowledge, great life experience, skill. At the same time, the problem is not a guide that describes everything from thread to needle, but often encourages independent search for solutions.

This form of direct demand is also useful in that it teaches students to consult with fellow students in certain situations, especially when difficulties arise. In turn, pedagogues should teach themselves to value students' requests for advice, not just to tell their own reaction, but to provide natural support to their younger peers.

Demand is a hidden form and one of the subtlest means of inspiring students to certain actions. Sha'ma is a kind of conditional reduction of previously used, well-known demands, demands whose meaning cannot be revealed. For an experienced pedagogue, sometimes it is enough to ask students a stare, a movement of the eyebrows, a rhetorical question to ensure that students perform the necessary actions. In certain conditions, the sham plays the role of a "hidden" form of demand, which is understandable only to two people and does not attract the attention of others.

A conditional requirement is that an activity that is pleasant for the child appears as a motivating factor for an unpleasant or difficult activity.

In conclusion, it should be said that what communication methods are chosen for a child from a young age, from the period of his early formation, and to what extent the factors affecting his upbringing are used appropriately, will be of great importance in his personal development in the future. This is one of the most important tasks of parents, then preschool educators, and then teachers and pedagogues.

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